

Audio file

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Transcript

Speaker 1

Hello, my name is Anna Makarzi, and I'm studying a Masters in Source Engineering at Blegging Institute of Technology. And I'm conducting research to investigate our developers in maintainer's physical liabilities in the open source dependent project. And this is given the background of supply chain attacks being carried out through open source dependent that if it comes to COMO. And my study focuses on developers from ecosystem and web framework, mainly Django, next to GS, OpenBoot, Laraville, and Ruby on Rail. And just some ethical issues. Participation in this research can withdraw from the industry at any time. We will not retain any personal data or identifiable information. Your e-mail address and will not be published or shared with anyone. You can skip any questions that you're not comfortable answering. And your response will remain anonymous and will not be linked to the projects that you're representing. The interview will be recorded and kept for the duration of the study to allow the unified authenticity of the reported data after which they will be deleted. Okay, and then before we start. So please introduce yourself. Tell us how many years of experience we have as a developer. and if you're a competitor or maintain of any open source projects, and then tell us also the web framework that you're using and how many years you have experience with that web framework.

Speaker 2

Oh, so I students and of course from that I am a social engineer I've been uh websites you've been Java spring boost specifically so uh I've only used uh as a framework I haven't used other languages and I've been using spring boost for two years now yeah and then all right thank you.

Speaker 1

So in your projects, what is it that you do? Do you contribute code? Do you also maybe do pull requests, make pull requests, be it do testing or maybe trade issues to accept tickets? What do you do in those projects?

Speaker 2

So when I am working on a personal project, I don't have to. merge or pull request with anyone so it's usually just pushing to GitHub but you know working with the team which I do most of the time we have to pull request merge request get on meetings discuss about the changes that you've done yeah that's how that's how I go about about it okay.

Speaker 1

And the projects that you work on are they client projects like commercial projects or are they open?

Speaker 2

No, they are for client.

Speaker 1

For client, all right. Okay, and within this project, is anyone responsible for security, say the security team or security is handled by the developer?

Speaker 2

Security is handled by the developers. I haven't been in a team where we are like the front end developer, the back end, the security pattern. We're usually the front end developer, the back end developer, and maybe the designer. Yeah. So I'm here to work with in a team where we have a, we have a cyber security portion.

Speaker 1

So in your screen, you also use other framework or ecosystems, maybe javascript library for funding and stuff.

Speaker 2

Is Google specifically? No, but I've interacted with Javascript library in scenarios where I've had to build the front end myself. So I'll have to use like Javascript frameworks, like. but yeah. like, yeah, no, yeah.

Speaker 1

So when you're working with your, in your projects, you install other dependencies in your Spring Boot projects? Apart from Spring Boot itself.

Speaker 2

Yeah, that's, oh no, no. Okay, we use, Okay, when I'm working on a Spring Boost project, I will install dependencies from Marvin. Now, I don't know if that is going to answer your question.

Speaker 1

Yes, that's okay. Okay. And when you're using this spring, spring, okay, Marvin dependencies. Are you aware of probably the dangers they might present to your project in terms of security? Suppose maybe the vulnerability within themselves.

Speaker 2

Yeah. So, okay, I haven't had such questions. And it's because when, okay, when you're installing a dependency into your voice, when you go to the library, they they show the versions of the dependencies, and then some versions have been masked. But like they've been known to have vulnerability. So it has been indicated there with a red, like red words. So I wouldn't speak a version that has dependencies. I'll only pick one that is stable enough. Yeah. So I yeah. So I wouldn't pick one that has vulnerability.

Speaker 1

Okay, you wouldn't pick. Okay. All right. Are you aware of supply chain attacks and that they can be carried out through the defenses this you are using in your projects and also their effects on projects?

Speaker 2

I wasn't aware of this, but I found this recently when I was preparing for this interview. I was trying to see maybe what exactly you are trying to uh this is your boat and then I found out about this application so yeah I only found us you.

Speaker 1

Listen all right okay you said when you're installing uh the dependent is at the start uh when when you go to the site they show you whether everything is good sometimes Vulnerabilities may be discovered maybe after you have installed them. How do you identify dependencies with vulnerabilities within your project?

Speaker 2

I don't think I have a ways of identifying that. I haven't had such a guess or maybe I haven't heard of this. I don't know. I haven't dealt with that before.

Speaker 1

Okay. So you said use GitHub and GitHub with tools like Dependabot and also GitHub technically advisors. Do you use those ones in your project just to monitor the dependencies that you're using within your project?

Speaker 2

No, I didn't know you can do this. I haven't.

Speaker 1

You haven't used GitHub Dependabot. Okay. Okay. You mentioned working in a team with others. Um do you have any like uh CI scripts that you run? I couldn't have integration for you to be able to uh make and also, you know, run on your code before.

Speaker 2

Um but I haven't okay in relation to the virtual I was in the one handling in that place okay but I know but my my other teammates may work my my work on this to make sure this um all right.

Speaker 1

Okay so uh sometimes uh okay this is common between the open source uh well that developers may create a package uh get used and then they somehow that happens and they abandon that project and stop maintaining it So what I'm interested in, after you, after maybe you checked to see where the dependence was being maintained when you first installed it, and then after you're using, do you ever check to see whether that dependence is still being maintained or if you're still working, you just go on your?

Speaker 2

I don't, I don't check as long as my code is burning.

Speaker 1

Okay, as long as the code is running. Okay, and do you update dependencies to new applications within your project? Or do you just keep whatever you use that is running it better?

Speaker 2

I've never updated my dependencies.

Speaker 1

You've never updated.

Speaker 2

Yeah, because when I did the version, I'll pick the most stable version. even when yeah I I haven't heard that in every way I need to update my dependency oh.

Speaker 1

Okay, so what security checks do you have for your project to make sure that there are no attacks that happen either through dependencies or any other way?

Speaker 2

I don't. I okay, the only security part I work on you where I like working on the security of the web, the application itself. But I've never touched a voice It's just coming from dependencies. I wasn't aware of this.

Speaker 1

So you are not aware. Okay. So when you work with Javascript dependent, I know most Npm packages we can end up deprecated and not being supported. Just mentioned that you don't update dependency. So How do you deal with those dependencies that are not in support?

Speaker 2

Yeah, so when I was talking about not updating dependencies, I was talking about the dependencies from Spring Boot. But in JavaScript, I've worked with project. And after I leave it for a while, and then I come back, I find that, OK, I usually get a notification from the terminal. Like, some dependencies have been, maybe, and then once that happens, I'll try to find a way to update them or remove those dependencies in my projects. Yeah, so I think for JavaScript, it's good because I usually get informed. I'll know if the dependencies are.

Speaker 1

Yeah. Okay, from from I know, javascript says Npm audit to. If you can run to check whether your dependence is secure, or you have some vulnerabilities. Python is pip audit. Does maven or Java have any commands that you can use to audit the dependencies within your project?

Speaker 2

I'm not aware of this. I don't know. I haven't worked with this. But I knew about NPM or this because I've used it when maybe I'm building content for my website. But for Java, I don't know. I've never used something like that in Java.

Speaker 1

Oh, all right. So you said you only researched a supply chain attack when you told my. Okay, is there anything that you would now change with the way that you are handling dependencies now? Even that you now know that there could be some vulnerabilities within your dependencies.

Speaker 2

Yeah. Yeah, I was just really thinking about that. So I after after trying to do research on what you are discussing about. So okay, the practices that I think I can apply to in my project is to specify. Okay, before I add the dependencies. I try to check the versions if they're okay and then when I'm adding them to my projects I specify the version so that they know so that it can like I can predict how they're going to work like I know that if I use this version then my app is going to work like correctly yeah and then I'll try to check about to check on common vulnerabilities and exposure but Okay, that's when I was applying it, but maybe halfway because I used to only check when I'm when I'm pulling the dependencies to my projects, but I didn't follow up to check if dependency is being maintained. So I think that is something that I can improve on.

Speaker 1

Awesome. You mentioned, but do you have any thoughts on using the prob in your in your projects so that you can probably do this automatically using automated?

Speaker 2

Yeah. Yeah. This is something that I'm yes to learn. I wanted to. Okay, I said we have exam. So I have to be there, for example, I wanted to to study about it and practice this. after I'm done with my exam, because I do believe on how to use it somewhere in like that. Yeah. Actually, it plays a very big role, so I have to learn. It's just like what you're going.

Speaker 1

All right. You mentioned that you're a student. What are you studying?

Speaker 2

Mathematics and computer science.

Speaker 1

Okay. And what level are you in?

Speaker 2

I'm in India, second semester.

Speaker 1

I think. Okay. So I think that's all I had to ask you. I didn't quite a number of questions, but they dependent on what you said before.

Speaker 2

Okay.

Speaker 1

Yes. But thank you so much for taking your time to take part in this interview. this has been insightful for my research.

Speaker 2

No I will thank you for having me you're welcome what's your no I wanted to ask you a question okay no okay these are just I don't know if you have to record it no I'm trying to get uh Okay, I feel like it's interesting. What you're researching about is interesting because I never even thought about it and I'm sure so many developers are not even aware of that. Silly, how did this, how would you use this researching about this? Like how did, how did you, what made you start researching about this?

Speaker 1

All right, so I'll stop recording and then we can talk.